

A STUDY ON CONSUMER PERCEPTION TOWARDS ONLINE GROCERY SHOPPING IN CHENNAI

Dr. R.MEGANATHAN, M.Com.,M.Phil.,SLET.,MBA.,PH.D Dean, Mohamed Sathak
College of Arts & Science, Sholinganallur, Chennai-600119. Tamil Nadu, India.

ABSTRACT

Consumers are playing an important role in online shopping. The increasing use of Internet by the younger generation in India provides an emerging prospect for online retailers. If online retailers know the factors affecting Indian consumers' buying behaviour, and the associations between these factors and type of online buyers, then they can further develop their marketing strategies to convert potential customers into active ones. The main objective of the study is to determine the customer perception towards online grocery shopping in Chennai. The sources of data used in this project report are both primary and secondary data. Descriptive research type is used for this research. Primary data consists of original information gathered from sample size of 200 respondents residing in Chennai, Tamil Nadu through Google forms, which is posted in social networking sites. Survey method is used to collect the primary data. The major findings of the study are 29% of respondents quoted the reason for choosing the online shopping is to purchase unique and special articles, and they want to find the best price of the product. The outcome of the research paper also revealed that the demographic variables, such as gender, age group don't have influence of the factors of customer satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Buyer behaviour, Consumer perception, Online grocery Shopping, Onlineshopping

INTRODUCTION

The term "perception" can be defined as the ability to derive meaning. Derived from the word "perceive", it refers to the ability of giving meaning to whatever is sensed by our sense organs. Schiffman defines it as "the process by which an individual selects, organizes, and interprets stimuli into a meaningful and coherent picture of the world." The term customer perception can be defined as, "a marketing concept that encompasses a customer's impression, awareness and/or consciousness about a company or its offerings. Customer perception is typically affected by advertising, reviews, public relations, social media, personal experiences and other channels." Consumer perceptions of price, value, quality are the pivotal determinants of shopping behaviour.

Internet is changing the way consumers shop and buy goods and services, and has rapidly evolved into a global phenomenon. Many companies have started using the Electronic Commerce with the aim of cutting marketing costs, thereby reducing the price of their products and services in order to stay ahead in highly competitive markets. Companies also use the Internet to convey communicate and disseminate information, to sell the product, to take feedback and also to conduct satisfaction surveys with customers. Customers use the Internet not only to buy the product online, but also to compare prices, product features and after sale service facilities they will receive if they purchase the product from a particular store. Many experts are optimistic about the prospect of online business.

In addition to the tremendous potential of the E-commerce market, the Internet provides a unique opportunity for companies to more efficiently reach existing and potential customers. Although most of the revenue of online transactions comes from business-to-business commerce, the practitioners of business-to-consumer commerce should not lose confidence. It has been more than a decade since business-to-consumer E-commerce first evolved. Scholars and practitioners of electronic commerce constantly strive to gain an improved insight into consumer behavior in cyberspace. Along with the development of E-retailing, researchers continue to explain E-consumers behavior from different perspectives. Many of their studies have posited new emergent factors or assumptions which are based on the traditional models of consumer behavior, and then examine their validity in the Internet context. This study is an attempt to know the consumer perception towards purchasing grocery item through online.

Online grocery shopping is a way of buying food and other household necessities using a web-based shopping service. There are two basic methods that people can use to purchase these items online. One is to order them from a local grocery store that participates

in online shopping. A customer can then arrange for a home delivery directly from the store, or he can pick up his order at the store once an employee has assembled it. Another common practice is to order groceries from a large company, such as Amazon or Netgrocer, that will ship the items to one's home.

INDUSTRY PROFILE

Proving that no sector of the retail market is safe from the online shopping revolution, it is now possible for the humble hometown grocery store to become digitized and available on your smartphone, tablet, or computer. Just think no longer checkout lines, counting the number of items to see if you qualify for the Express Lane, forgetting your grocery list at home, or carrying heavy bags up your front steps. Online grocery shopping is dramatically changing the consumer's relationship with the food market and making a service that may have once felt luxurious into an everyday convenience.

An online grocery store is a website that allows users to purchase food over the Internet to be delivered to the person at a later time. Ordering food on the Internet is similar to ordering any other product--the desired food items can be searched for specifically, or one can browse through listings of products or sections, similar to sections one might walk through at an actual grocery store. The products offered by an online grocery store are identical to a normal grocery store. When one has finished shopping, checkout is made with a credit card, and the buyer must specify certain hours that he will be available to receive the food for delivery. Since Internet groceries must deliver the food to the customers, they typically pay a fee for delivery based on the amount of food they buy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

"India is among the fastest-growing markets and has been identified as one of the significant potential markets for the company,"

Vijayasarathy (2014), in his research used a sample of 281 consumers to test a model of consumer intention to use on-line shopping. The study found compatibility, usefulness, ease of use, and security to be significant predictors of attitude towards on-line shopping, but privacy was not. Another finding showed that intention to use on-line shopping was strongly influenced by attitude toward on-line shopping, normative beliefs, and self-efficacy.

Rainu Tan veer Singh (2012), he was undertaken the project in NiralaImex Inc. in Taiwanese market in selling of Indian grocery items to the local retailers & wholesaler in the Taiwanese market. The project first studied the attitude of customers towards online shopping, also determining the factors which influence the consumer to purchase goods and service. The second half of the project depicted the attributes of online shopping influencing

the purchase decision by the respondent. It also determined the issues regarding the online shopping. The third part of the project determines the purchase decision with respect to grocery. It determined the place preference of grocery shopping with respect to price, quality, variety, proximity and offers/ discounts. The project also recommended the business operational plan which works with contracting dealership with the local Kirana stores.

Muralikrishnan, B(2012), country manager at eBay's India in his article explains that Indian consumers toward buying high margin products such as clothes and shoes as is the trend among eBay shoppers in the West rather than electronic gadgets and books, which are the most popular choices now but command lower profit margins and are less frequent purchases. He depicted that India's nascent e-commerce market, which till recently was largely limited to people buying train, flight and movie tickets, is in the middle of a surge as a younger, tech-savvy middle class increasingly takes to shopping online in a country seeing rapid growth in Internet usage. Consulting firm Technopak predicts a \$70-billion annual market by 2020, up from \$600 million now, which is just 0.05% of global online shopping. EBay itself estimates India's online shopping market in 2012 will grow close to 100%.

George Adamidis et al (2016), in this paper, the authors discussed about specific aspect of shopping; grocery shopping. Grocery shopping is an essential and routine type of consumer behavior, which over the last few decades has undergone major changes due to the rapid evolution of technology. E-grocery is the new form of grocery shopping, which allows consumers to order products via the Internet from the convenience of their house. The evolution of online and in-store grocery shopping is largely determined by the motives and the behavior of consumers. The aim of this paper is to investigate and explain Cypriot consumer's perceptions and responses towards online grocery shopping. A survey that utilized a self-administered questionnaire for collecting data from respondents, was conducted at the capital of Cyprus; Nicosia. Cypriot consumers are not ready yet to accept e-grocery shopping as an alternative to traditional grocery shopping. Based on the findings of this survey, "the good quality of the products offered" and "a money back guarantee" can be decided upon by the e-grocers as it seems to be the better risk relievers. In addition, "the competitive prices of the products", "safe dealings through the Internet" and "loyalty to well-known products" may consist of highly effective incentives to increase the number of online shoppers.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY:

Primary objective:

- To study about customer perception towards online grocery shopping in Chennai.

Secondary objectives:

- To find out the factors which influence the attitude of customers towards online grocery shopping in Chennai
- To find out the preferences of the consumer regarding the attributes of consumer online shopping website
- To identify the issues faced by the user while online shopping.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

This research collected the primary data through online survey using Google forms, where direct interaction between researcher and respondents were not possible.

Since the online survey using Google forms were designed and posted in Social networking sites, the samples were not restricted based on geographical location.

The sample size 200 may not be suitable to enumerate the true population.

Other limitation caused in the market research was that the research will only study the consumer perception towards online grocery shopping and not the dealers, wholesalers or retailers' perception towards online grocery shopping which acts as an agent to the online retail industry to support its business operations.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY:

The sources of data used in this project report are both primary and secondary data. Descriptive research type is used for this research. Primary data consists of original information gathered from sample size of 200 respondents residing in Chennai, Tamil Nadu through Google forms, which is posted in social networking sites. Survey method is used to collect the primary data. The major parameter of interest is the subgroup of people who are working professional and tech savvy having an experience in online shopping. The two other subsidiary parameters of interest are, the respondent should also have an experience grocery shopping and the female respondent who have an online shopping experience. The convenience sampling technique is used for the research, so the respondents who are interested to participate in this research can record their responses.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Analysis and interpretation are central steps in the research process. The aim of the analysis is to organize, classify and summarize the collected data so that they can be better comprehended and interpreted to give answers to the questions that triggered the research.

Interpretation is the search for the broader meaning of findings. Analysis is not fulfilled without interpretation; and interpretation cannot proceed without analysis. So, both are inter dependent.

FREQUENCY ANALYSIS:

Percentage analysis is one of the statistical measures used to describe the characteristics of the sample or population in totality. Percentage analysis involves computing measures of variables selected of the study and its finding will give easy interpretation for the reader.

Table 1 Classification of respondents based on Age, Gender and Occupation

S. No	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1.	AGE:		
	18-25 years	76	38.0
	25-30 years	81	40.5
	Above 30 years	43	21.5
2.	GENDER:		
	Male	144	72
	Female	56	28
3.	OCCUPATION:		
	Student	52	26
	Employee(Private /Public)	88	44
	Business	60	30
4.	MARITAL STATUS		
	Single	74	37.0
	Married	126	63.0
5	SUPPORTING DEVICE FOR INTERNET CONNECTION		
	Desktop	35	17.5
	Laptop	61	30.5
	Mobile	56	28.0
	Tablet	48	24.0

(Source: Primary Data)

From the above Table 1.It is inferred that, 40.5% of respondents were belongs to the age group of 25 – 30 years. Majority (72%) of the respondents were Male and remaining were Female. 44% of the respondents are working in Private /Public companies. Majority of

the respondents were married. 30.5% of respondents are using internet connection through Laptop computer.

Table 2 Frequency table – Consumer perception

S. No	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Frequency of Online shopping		
	Daily	30	15.0
	Weekly once	58	29.0
	Monthly once	85	42.5
	Rarely never	27	13.5
2	Why need to online shopping		
	Home delivery	44	22.0
	Unique and special	58	29.0
	Find the best price	57	28.5
	No time	41	20.5
3	Online shopping is beneficial		
	Yes	90	45.0
	No	110	55.0
4	Shopping in grocery items		
	Local market	28	13
	Nearby Retail shops	58	29
	Wholesalers	46	23
	Super market	46	23
	Online shopping	24	12

(Source: Primary Data)

Table 2 presents that, 42.5% of respondents are doing online shopping monthly once, and whereas around 15% of the respondents responded that they are doing online shopping daily. Around 29% of respondents quoted the reason for choosing the online shopping is to purchase unique and special articles, and they want to find the best price of the product. The interesting as well as contradicting fact is about 55% of the respondents opined that the online shopping is not beneficial, whereas the remaining 45% of the respondents were opined that it is beneficial. 29% of respondents buy grocery items from nearby retail shops.

MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION:**Table 3: Mean and SD of factors of consumer satisfaction**

S. No	Parameters	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	User friendly	3.03	.690
2	Adequate search option	4.12	.796
3	Product assortments/categories	4.14	.764
4	Payment options	4.24	.718
5	Cash on delivery	4.97	.793
6	Offers and discounts	4.44	.769
7	Free shipments	4.27	.724
8	Login facility	4.33	.712

(Source: Primary Data)

From the above table 3, it is inferred that the respondents perceive higher level of satisfaction with respect to adequate search option, Product categories, payment options, cash on delivery, offers and discounts, free shipments, login facility with the mean value of above 4.00, while compared to user friendliness with the mean value of 3.03.

INDEPENDENT SAMPLE T-TEST:

Hypothesis i:

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between male and female respondents with respect to the factors of consumer satisfaction.

Table 4.Independent sample t test for significant difference between male and female respondents with respect to the factors of the consumer satisfaction

S. No	Particulars	Gender	Mean	Std. Deviation	t value	p value
1.	User friendly	Male	1.62	0.690	1.936	0.054
		Female	1.41	0.654		
2.	Adequate search option	Male	2.05	0.796	0.183	0.855
		Female	2.07	0.783		
3.	Product assortments/categories	Male	2.10	0.764	0.569	0.570
		Female	2.04	0.762		
4.	Payment options	Male	2.04	0.718	1.352	1.758
		Female	2.20	0.749		
5.	Cash on delivery	Male	2.09	0.793	1.728	0.86
		Female	2.88	0.788		
6.	Net Banking	Male	2.07	0.781	1.011	0.313
		Female	1.95	0.749		
7.	Debit and Credit cards	Male	2.17	0.769	2.608	0.316
		Female	1.86	0.773		
8.	Offers and discounts	Male	2.10	0.687	2.167	0.235
		Female	2.34	0.695		
9.	Free shipments	Male	2.12	0.724	0.550	0.064
		Female	2.15	0.796		
10	Login facility	Male	2.13	0.712	0.578	0.112
		Female	2.20	0.699		
11.	Order confirm screen	Male	2.12	0.780	1.541	0.088
		Female	1.93	0.783		

(Source: Primary data)

From the above table 4, it is inferred that all the factors of consumer satisfaction are having the p value greater than 0.05, so null hypothesis is accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance. Hence it is concluded that there is no significant difference between male and female respondents with respect to perception of consumer satisfaction towards online grocery stores.

HYPOTHESIS III: CHI SQUARE TEST

Null Hypothesis: There is no association between gender and interest to buy grocery items throughonline in future.

Table 5: Chi-square test for association between gender and interest to buy grocery itemsthrough online in future.

Gender	Interest to buy grocery through online in future			Total	Value	P value
	Yes	No	Maybe			
Male	45	52	47	144	3.926	0.140
Female	10	22	24	56		
Total	55	74	71	200		

(Source: Primary data)

From the above table 5, it is inferred that p value is 0.140, which is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted and alternate hypothesis is rejected at 5 % level of significance. Hence it is concluded that there is no association between gender and interest to buy grocery through online in future.

DISCUSSIONS:

- 42.5% of respondents were doing online shopping monthly once, whereas around 15% of the respondents responded that they are doing online shopping daily. Around 29% of respondents quoted the reason for choosing the online shopping is to purchase unique and special articles, and they want to find the best price of the product.
- The interesting as well as contracting fact is about 55% of the respondents opined that the online shopping is not beneficial, whereas the remaining 45% of the respondents were opined it is beneficial.
- The data also determines the factors which will be beneficial for the consumer to shop grocery online which are variety at one shop, saves times and avoid long queues.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Instead of going the regular e Commerce way of Grocery shopping, the firm should startup by bringing existing retailers online.
- For the purchase of the grocery item user can choose their nearby Kirana Store from the listed stores along with a convenient time of the delivery.
- The local store would be informed about the order and it would be delivered to theaddress at the time mentioned with the payment of cash only on delivery.

CONCLUSION:

From the above data analysis, it can be concluded that consumer buys goods from the online shopping website on the basis of factors like offers and discounts, variety of product available, free home delivery, website user friendliness and cash of delivery payment option. The outcome of the research paper also revealed that the demographic variables, such as gender, age group don't have influence of the factors of customer satisfaction. The customers expects improvement user friendliness of the website, in order to choose online as a medium to buy grocery items rather than shopping of grocery with the traditional method. Out of the agreed respondent to buy online grocery, most of the respondent would think that it would be beneficial to shop grocery online on the basis of factors like easy to order, variety, discounts/ offers, saves time and avoid long queues.

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